

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

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Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

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**Public Executive Summary of deliverable [D5.2: Gram-scale
melanin-like polymers using oxidase-peroxidase
cascade system name of deliverable]**

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Executive summary log

Submission	31-01-2025
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Main achievements/outcomes

Deliverable 5.2 concludes the work on one of OXIPRO's four innovation pillars, the cosmetic case. The specific objective of this case is validating 1 laccase-based production of melanin-like polymers for sun care product formulation.

Organic UV filters used in sunscreens pollute coastal waters, damaging corals (bleaching) and bioaccumulating in marine biota where they can impair growth and reproduction (Watkins & Sallach, 2021). Melanin, a family of heterogeneous polymeric pigments, is present in all life forms providing a variety of functions, such as pigmentation, radical scavenging and radiation protection (Cao et al., 2021). Currently used UV-filters are small molecules that can penetrate the skin, while polymeric UV-filters have shown low toxicity to algae coral and mice due to their high molecular weight (Zeng et al., 2023). OXIPRO aims to enzymatically produce melanin-like polymers as environmentally friendly UV filters compatible with conventional sunscreen formulations thus, ensuring a rapid uptake by sunscreen formulators.

The present report shows the successful development in OXIPRO of a laccase-assisted bioprocess for synthesizing melanin-like polymers with potential as sun protection factor (SPF) boosters in sunscreens. This biocatalytic process is based on the laccase assisted polymerization of phenolic monomers. The reaction was initially established using a commercially available laccase combined with a selected mediator. The established synthetic route allowed the polymerization of a selected monomer into a phenolic polymer that shows significant SPF boosting effect. The enzymatic polymerization reaction was successfully scale-up to gram scale yield. The obtained SPF-boosting

polymer can be incorporated into sunscreen formulations however it imparts undesirable dark colour and its high solubility in water can lead to a fast wash off after application, future cosmetic formulations can be explored to overcome these limitations. In parallel, a in-silico bioprospecting of new laccases able to achieve polymerization of phenolic monomers was performed, leading to the identification of a new laccase with optimum activity for the developed synthesis of melanin-like polymers.

References

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